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COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF GEOLOGICAL ENGINEERING

PROJECT REPORT

**TOPIC: COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GPR AND ERT IN IMAGING SUBSURFACE
STRUCTURE**

PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE B.Sc. (ENG) DEGREE

SUBMITTED BY:

BOAMAH, AARON (2968720)

SARPONG, ANDY (2977220)

SARFO-APPAU, BERNICE (2977120)

YEBOAH, BENNETH KWAKYE (2978220)

SUPERVISOR:

DR. BUKARI ALI

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DECLARATION

We hereby declare that except for references to other people's works which have been duly acknowledged, this dissertation submitted to the Geological Engineering Department Board, College of Engineering, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, is the result of our own investigation and had not been presented for any other degree.

BOAMAH, AARON
(Student's name)

2968720
(Index Number)

.....
(Signature)

12/09/2024
.....
(Date)

SARPONG, ANDY
(Student's name)

2977220
(Index Number)

.....
(Signature)

12/09/2024
.....
(Date)

SARFO-APPAU, BERNICE
(Student's name)

2977120
(Index Number)

.....
(Signature)

12/09/2024
.....
(Date)

YEBOAH, BENNETH KWAKYE
(Student's name)

2978220
(Index Number)

.....
(Signature)

12/09/2024
.....
(Date)

I hereby declare that I have supervised these students in the undertaking of this project and confirm that these students have my permission to present it for assessment.

Dr. Bukari Ali
(Supervisor)

.....
(Signature)

Sept. 12, 2024
.....
(Date)

ABSTRACT

Understanding what lies beneath the earth's surface is important in many fields of study, including geotechnical, hydrogeology and geological engineering. This allows engineers to make informed decisions and allocate resources appropriately. Typically, most reliable subsurface investigations involve invasive methods -e.g. drilling- which are expensive and time consuming but provide only discrete information. However, geophysical methods have revolutionised subsurface imaging; they are non-invasive, less expensive, continuous and fast. The GPR and ERT are typical examples which are studied under this project to see how they can complement each other in subsurface investigations. While ERT maps the subsurface resistivity distribution, the GPR uses reflected electromagnetic waves to image the subsurface layering. This work is a comparative study of the ERT and GPR in imaging subsurface structure. Five traverse lines were investigated on the KNUST campus using the dipole-dipole array for the ERT and time triggering mode for the GPR. The ERT provided resistivity profiles, showing three (3) distinct resistivity zones: a mixture of very low and low resistivity zone extending from the surface to about 5 m; very high resistivity zone occurring at 5 – 20 m; and high resistivity zone, which extends beyond 20 m. The GPR survey identified three distinct layers -layer 1 of strong reflections from the surface up to 5 m deep, layer 2 of medium reflections from 5 – 20 m, and layer 3 of weak reflections beyond 20 m. Comparing the GPR and ERT images, layer 1 of strong reflections appears to correspond to the mixture of low and very low resistivity zone -a completely weathered granitic unit extending from the surface to about 5 m depth; layer 2 of medium reflections correspond closely to the very high resistivity zones at 5 – 20 m -a highly weathered granitic unit; and layer 3 of weak reflections corresponding to the high resistivity zone beyond 20 m -a moderately to slightly weathered granitic unit (suspected to be bedrock). This study demonstrates that integrating GPR and ERT may offer a fast and inexpensive method of subsurface imaging, enhancing subsurface investigations.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Understanding what lies beneath the Earth's surface is important in various fields, especially in geological and civil engineering. Knowledge of subsurface formations provide valuable information about soil types, subsurface layering, geological structures, and groundwater resources. Traditionally, most reliable subsurface investigations use invasive methods such as drilling and other forms of excavations, which are costly and time-consuming, and often provide discrete spatial coverage. However, geophysical techniques have revolutionized subsurface imaging by offering non-invasive, high-resolution alternatives. Among the array of geophysical techniques, Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) and Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) have evolved as prominent methods for imaging subsurface formations (Beauvais et al., 2004; Sass et al., 2008). ERT maps subsurface distribution of electrical resistivity (Sass et al., 2008), providing insights into subsurface formations -e.g. geological structures, and groundwater distribution. By contrast, GPR utilises electromagnetic waves to penetrate the ground and analyse reflected and refracted signals, enabling the detection of subsurface features such as buried objects and stratigraphic layers (Daniels, 2000). The effectiveness of GPR and ERT in imaging subsurface structure depends on several variables, such as the equipment utilised and its depth of penetration, and the properties of the target material (Daniels, 2000; Baker et al., 2007; Beauvais et al., 2004). While both methods offer significant advantages, it is crucial to acknowledge their limitations as well- low resolution in shallow subsurface for ERT and limited depth of penetration for GPR. This project aims to compare the images of ERT and GPR in subsurface imaging and explore potential integration of the two techniques to enhance results and interpretation.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT AND JUSTIFICATION

Understanding the subsurface structure is important in civil and geological engineering; it helps engineers make informed decisions and allocate resources appropriately. Invasive methods of subsurface investigations are expensive, destructive, and may not always be applicable. Geophysical methods are non-invasive, fast, continuous and generally, less expensive, but they are generally not diagnostic. GPR and ERT are becoming popular in subsurface imaging, but they measure different physical quantities –dielectric permittivity and resistivity, respectively.

This project seeks to compare the images of ERT and GPR, find correlations between them to see if they can complement each other in imaging the subsurface structure.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this work is to study the images generated by the GPR and ERT techniques in imaging subsurface structure to see the similarities and differences between them and how they can complement each other in understanding subsurface structures. The specific objectives are to:

- determine the subsurface layering/structure using the GPR,
- determine the subsurface resistivity distribution using the ERT, and
- compare images from the GPR and ERT and establish a correlation between them.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 DESCRIPTION OF STUDY AREA (KNUST)

The Oforikrom Municipal Assembly is home to Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology. It is located 13 km east of Kumasi and stretches between latitudes $6^{\circ} 39' 30''$ and $6^{\circ} 42' 0''$ N and longitudes $1^{\circ} 32' 0''$ and $1^{\circ} 35' 30''$ W (Fig. 2.1). The Wiwi River crosses the roughly 18 squared km of diverse topography that makes up the KNUST campus. There are 44,122 students in KNUST (KNUST, 2018).

Figure 2.1: An image of the study area (KNUST) and its environs

2.1.1 Geology of KNUST

Kumasi is primarily underlain by the middle Precambrian rocks of the Lower Birimian (metasediments) and Upper Birimian (metavolcanics). These Birimian rocks developed about 2.25-2.02 Ga during the Eburnean orogeny. KNUST is predominantly underlain by granitoids (Kesse, 1985). Geological map of KNUST is shown in Figure 2.2. Most of the muscovite and biotite-rich basin-type granitoids on the KNUST campus have a peculiar foliation. These basin type granitoids vary in the strength of metamorphism, resulting in a texture and composition that spans from normal granites to granitic gneisses (Ruddock, 1967).

Figure 2.2: Geological map of the study area, KNUST (Callistus, 2015)

2.1.2 Vegetation And Climate

The study site, KNUST, falls within the wet sub-equatorial climate. With an average humidity of 84.16 percent at sunrise and 60 percent at sunset, the average minimum and maximum temperatures are 21.5 and 30.7 degrees Celsius, respectively (Ghana Statistical Services, 2014). The metropolis lies in the wet semi-deciduous southeast ecological zone, which is a transitional forest zone. The study area features a thoughtful interaction plan in a green setting (KNUST, 2018).

2.2 OVERVIEW OF GEOPHYSICAL METHODS

Geophysical methods are non-destructive methods used to study the physical properties of the earth. These methods include seismic, gravity, magnetic, electric, and electromagnetic methods, just to mention a few. In geophysical prospecting, the purpose is to obtain information of the shallow (i.e. <10km) subsurface using various physical tools (Erkan, 2008). A general listing of the methods with some of their properties are given in Table 2.1.

Among the various geophysical methods, ERT and GPR will be utilised in this project for imaging subsurface structure. In ERT and GPR, the physical properties investigated are the electrical (i.e. the resistivity distribution) and electromagnetic properties of subsurface materials, respectively.

Table 2.1: Geophysical prospecting methods and their properties (Erkan, 2008)

<i>Geophysical Method</i>	<i>Measured property</i>	<i>Investigated physical property</i>	<i>Main practical obstacle</i>
Gravimetry	Acceleration vector and its gradient	Density contrast	Very little differences in the density of rocks
Magnetostatic	Magnetic field vector	Magnetic permeability	Rocks with poor magnetic strength
DC resistivity	Electric potential change	Resistivity	Rock resistivity causes a low penetration depth
Magneto telluric	Amplitudes of electromagnetic fields	Resistivity	Rocks conductivity causes rapid attenuation
Electromagnetic induction	Phase/amplitude change of the magnetic field	Resistivity Dielectric permittivity	Rocks conductivity causes rapid attenuation
Electromagnetic radiation (GPR)	Electromagnetic travel time	Contrasts in electromagnetic wave impedance	Rocks conductivity causes rapid attenuation
Seismic refraction	Seismic travel time	Seismic velocity	Seismic wave attenuation
Seismic reflection	Seismic travel time	Contrasts in acoustic wave impedance	Seismic wave attenuation

2.3 APPLICATION OF GEOPHYSICAL METHOD

The Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) and Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) are two non-invasive geophysical techniques widely used for imaging subsurface structure. Both methods have been extensively applied in various fields including hydrogeology, civil engineering, mining, and environmental monitoring (Daniels, 2000; Bizhani et al., 2020).

The geophysical resistivity method relies on how the earth responds to the flow of electric current. The main use of this technique is in groundwater prospecting (Barker, 1981; Gazoty et al., 2012). According to Reynolds (2011), the physical properties of lithology or stratigraphy have an impact on how electrical current moves through the earth. These physical properties include the degree of water saturation, mineral composition, and porosity (i.e. the presence or absence of voids). This method works well for investigating various subsurface materials because of variations in resistivity brought about by these properties. Groundwater exploration and subsurface structure imaging have made extensive use of the electrical resistivity method

(Barker, 1981; Schmutz et al., 2010; Gazoty et al., 2012; Wemegah et al., 2017). ERT has been used in hydrogeological and geotechnical applications by Loke (1999). and in environmental research (Wemegah et al., 2017) and mining (Tsiboah and Grant, 2009). Generally, electrical resistivity technique plays important role in investigating and exploring for earth resources such as clay materials, coal, as well as mineral resources such as gold (Tsiboah and Grant, 2009). This is because these materials produce significant resistivity signatures compared to their host rocks. Furthermore, several investigations where the electrical resistivity method was applied in the identification and mapping of several subsurface structures were described by Telford et al. (1990). This method is useful for delineating structures and intrusions within unconsolidated sediments, as Telford et al. (1976) showed.

For imaging subsurface structure, other geophysical methods, such as Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), is frequently used. GPR operates on the principle of transmitting and receiving reflected EM waves as they travel into the subsurface. Variations in the properties of subsurface materials affect the reflected signals recorded by GPR, exposing subsurface properties such as moisture content, material types, and the boundaries between layers (Reynolds, 2011). This has made it possible for the GPR approach to be widely employed for subsurface investigations in a variety of sectors, such as groundwater mapping and mineral exploration. Furthermore, it has been used to characterize the subsurface lithostratigraphy. In the subsurface of Eastern Senegal, for example, Beauvais et al. (2004) used GPR to analyse two-stepped lateritic weathering systems and found ferricrete layers at depths of 5 - 7 m. Similarly, Davis and Annan (1989) used the GPR approach for lithostratigraphic studies to map soil and identify groundwater by identifying differences in their dielectric properties. Furthermore, the dielectric characteristics of various geologic formations and structures have been investigated using GPR (Martinez and Brynes, 2002). Through this method, it is possible to determine the electrical conductivity and dielectric polarization of these materials. Huggenberger (1993) looked at subsurface geological features such as folds, joints, faults, and fractures using the GPR technique.

For imaging subsurface structure, several studies have compared GPR and ERT (Sass et al., 2008; Beauvais et al., 2004; Reynolds, 2011; Jan, 2018). Some key findings from these studies are that ERT is more appropriate for deeper, more resistive structures, whereas GPR is more effective in identifying shallow targets (Beauvais et al., 2004; Sass et al., 2008). In addition, GPR can produce precise subsurface image in 2D, as well as accurate depth estimations and information about buried materials beneath the surface (Daniels, 2000). Also, compared to

ERT, GPR provides a greater spatial resolution (Daniels, 2000; Jan, 2018; Beauvais et al., 2004).

2.4 GROUND PENETRATING RADAR (GPR)

GPR, is a low-cost, high-resolution, non-destructive geophysical method primarily used to explore the earth's shallow subsurface. GPR operates on the principle of transmitting electromagnetic waves into the ground and analysing reflected and refracted signals, enabling the detection of subsurface features such as buried objects and stratigraphic layers (Daniels, 2000).

In GPR, electromagnetic waves are sent and received by a transmitter and receiver antenna pair (Fig. 2.3). The reflected pulses are recorded as functions of time and the position of the antenna pair along a survey line. From a transmitting antenna, electromagnetic waves (1 - 1000 MHz), are radiated into the ground and the contrast in permittivity between the background material and the target of interest (or the contrast between layers) causes reflection and refraction of EM waves resulting in the identification and imaging of subsurface features (Young et al., 2002).

Figure 2.3: An image of Ground Penetrating Radar (Young et al., 2002)

The EM waves propagate through the subsurface at different speeds depending on the dielectric properties of subsurface materials (Daniels, 2000). If a wave encounters an object of different dielectric properties from the surrounding material, they are reflected to the surface and recorded by the receiving antenna or refracted and travels downward. Reflection occurs when EM waves hit a boundary where there is significant contrast in dielectric permittivity of subsurface materials. A higher permittivity contrast (e.g., soil to metal) results in strong reflections and a weaker contrast (e.g., soil to rock) causes weak reflections. Ideally, (1) the dielectric permittivity, (2) electrical conductivity, and (3) magnetic permeability cause waves

to be reflected, refracted, and attenuated, which in turn causes the waves to be recorded in the GPR receiver (Huggenberger, 1993; Daniels, 2000, Jan, 2018).

2.4.1 Dielectric Permittivity

According to Baker et al. (2007), dielectric permittivity is the capacity of a material to store electromagnetic energy and allow its passage when subjected to a field. This property determines the velocity at which electromagnetic waves travel through a material and can be determined in the laboratory or in-situ (Young et al., 2002). The basic idea behind employing GPR to explore the subsurface is the correlation between wave velocity and material properties. A signal travelling the same distance through two materials with different dielectric permittivity will arrive at different times because, as Table 2.2 illustrates, the EM velocity varies between materials with different dielectric properties. At or near sea level, the velocity of an electromagnetic wave in the Earth's atmosphere is 0.33 m/ns. All earth materials have relative permittivity values larger than that of air, hence any given earth material's EM wave velocity will be lower than that of air. Typical earth material velocities fall between 0.05 and 0.15 m/ns (Daniels et al., 1995).

Table 2.2: Relative permittivity (ϵ_r) and EM velocity of selected geologic materials (Baker et al., 2007)

Material	ϵ_r (Davis and Annan, 1989)	ϵ_r (Daniels, 1996)	Velocity (m/ns)	Material	ϵ_r (Daniels, 1996)	Velocity (m/ns)
Air	1	1	0.3	Soil, sandy wet	15 – 30	0.05 – 0.08
Fresh water	80	81	0.03	Soil, loamy dry	4 – 6	0.05 – 0.08
Sand, dry	3 – 5	4 – 6	0.12 – 0.17	Soil, loamy wet	15 – 30	0.07 – 0.09
Sand, wet	20 – 30	10 – 30	0.05 – 0.09	Soil clayey dry	4 – 6	0.12 – 0.15
Clays	5 – 40		0.05 – 0.13	Soil, clayey wet	10 – 15	0.08 – 0.09
Clay, dry	-	2 – 6	0.12 – 0.21	Granites*		0.12 – 0.15
Clay, wet	-	15 – 40	0.05 – 0.08	Granite, dry	5	0.13
Soil, sandy dry		4 – 6	0.12 – 0.15	Granite, wet	7	0.11

* The ϵ_r for the granites is reported by Davis and Annan (1989) as 4 -6

Materials with high permittivity (e.g., water) reduces wave velocity creating a longer trace, while low permittivity materials (e.g., air, dry sand) allow faster wave travel and hence a shorter trace (Daniels, 2000). A trace is a record of the electromagnetic wave's time-history as it moves from the transmitting antenna to the receiving antenna, i.e., the amount of time a wave takes to travel down to a target of interest and back to the surface (Daniels, 2000). The dielectric properties of subsurface rock and soil elements are linked to their moisture content and composition. Water and wet clay, which have higher dielectric values than rock and typical

soils, result in longer travel times of EM waves; the radar velocity decreases with increasing water saturation therefore reducing depth of penetration of EM waves (Young et al., 2002). According to Young et al. (2002), the inverse square root of the material's permittivity determines the EM velocity of the wave travelling through a material:

$$V_m = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}}, \dots\dots\dots 2.1$$

Determining the appropriate EM velocity of a material helps to improve the accuracy of depth estimations and interpretation of GPR results. GPR depth measurements rely on wave velocity, which is influenced by permittivity; higher permittivity results in shallow effective depth and vice versa (Young et al., 2002). Thus, if the trace and velocity of wave travelling through a medium is known, depth of buried object can be determined (Young et al., 2002):

$$D = \frac{cT}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} = \frac{V_m T}{2}, \dots\dots\dots 2.2$$

Where V_m = the velocity of the material, c = the velocity of light, ϵ_r = relative dielectric constant, and T = two-way travel time in nanoseconds (ns; 1 ns = 1 x 10⁹ seconds), D = depth of investigation.

2.4.2 Electrical Conductivity

The flow of electrical charges during the passage of an EM wave describes the electrical conductivity of a material which can greatly affect the attenuation of EM signals. Conductivity is one of the main factors affecting signal attenuation, which in turn governs the penetration depth. A high conductivity material will generally attenuate GPR signals rapidly and vice versa (Evans, 2010). Factors that increase conductivity include presence of saline water in materials and the presence of clay minerals. Hence, the presence of water and clay minerals can reduce the resolution and effective depth of penetration of a GPR survey (Evans, 2010).

2.4.3 Magnetic Permeability

The ability of material to support the formation of a magnetic field describes its magnetic permeability, which impacts the magnetic component of the EM wave (Telford et al, 1976). The changes in magnetic permeability, less common in most geologic materials, can affect wave speed and attenuation. In materials with high magnetic permeability (e.g., iron), EM waves may slow down, affecting the depth estimations and reflection intensity (Telford et al., 1976).

2.4.4 GPR frequency and Depth of Penetration

The depth of penetration of an EM wave also depends on the frequency of the wave. Low-frequency waves penetrate deeper into the subsurface (i.e., low-frequency waves are less

affected by attenuation as compared to high-frequency waves (energy loss due to absorption by the medium), allowing them to reach greater depths) but produce weaker reflections and resolution because of its low sensitivity to permittivity contrast between materials; however, high-frequency waves have a shallow depth of penetration with strong reflections and resolution due to its high sensitivity to small-scale permittivity contrast between materials. As such, there is significant variation in reflected signals across different frequencies (Baker et al., 2007).

The attenuation of the radar signal in subsurface media determines the depth of penetration, and there are three types of losses contributing to this attenuation -electrical, scattering, and spreading. Some factors influencing the attenuation of radar signals are the dielectric permittivity, electrical conductivity and frequency of the radar signals (Daniels, 2000; Salih et al., 2022). The penetration depth reduces as conductivity and frequency of radar signal increases, because signal strength decreases with depth due to faster loss of electromagnetic energy into heat (Daniels, 2000). Penetration can occasionally be as little as a few centimetres in soils that are damp, clay-rich, or have strong electrical conductivity (Salih et al., 2022) while good penetration can be attained down to a depth of up to 15 m in dry sandy soils or large, dry materials like concrete, granite, and limestone. While higher frequencies provide better resolution, they do not go as deep as lower frequencies (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3: Propagation depth and frequency used in GPR (Salih et al., 2022)

f_{ant} (MHz)	Suitable target size (m)	D_{ef} (m)	D_{ap} (m)	f_{ant} (MHz)	Suitable target size (m)	D_{ef} (m)	D_{ap} (m)
25	1.0	5 - 30	35 - 60	500	0.04	1 - 5	3 - 10
50	0.5	5 - 20	20 - 30	800	0.02	0.4 - 2	1 - 6
100	0.1 - 1.0	2 - 15	15 - 25	1000	0.01	0.05 - 2	0.5 - 4
250	0.50	1 - 10	5 - 15	1600	0.01	0.2 - 1	0.5 - 2

f_{ant} = Antennae frequency; D_{ef} = Effective depth; D_{ap} = Approximate penetration depth

2.4.5 GPR Survey Methods

When it comes to survey design, GPR involves various crucial elements, such as the data collection mode and antenna characteristics like frequency, spacing, and orientation (Baker et al., 2007). Usually, to achieve specific objectives, the data collection method is selected initially. The three main modes of data collection are: (1) transillumination, also called borehole radar, which is used for tomography and borehole research: (2) common offset (CO), which is used for reflection mapping: (3) common midpoint (CMP), which is frequently used to estimate wave velocities (Davis et al., 1989; Daniels, 2000).

By positioning the antennas side by side on the ground and gradually adjusting their separation with respect to a fixed point, i.e., the midway, two static antennas can be used in CMP surveys (Fig. 2.4a). Finding the slope of the direct wave reflection in relation to the offset distance and two-way travel time of the antennas allows one to compute the wave velocity (Daniels, 2000; Baker et al., 2007). The subsurface velocity estimations play a crucial role in estimating the depth to a target based on wave arrival times.

Figure 2.4: GPR data collection modes: (a) Common mid-point (CMP), (b) Common offset (CO) and (c) Transillumination mode (Baker et al., 2007)

Although CMP surveys are common for determining the velocity and dielectric structure of the subsurface, the majority of GPR surveys designed for near-surface applications are collected in common offset (CO) or reflection mode (Beauvais et al., 2004; Baker et al., 2007). In this mode, fixed spacing is maintained between antennas that are positioned on the ground and moved along a survey line at predetermined intervals (Fig. 2.4b). Along the survey line, reflection surveys are used to identify objects and/or surfaces with contrast in electromagnetic characteristics.

Transillumination is carried out in two boreholes by lowering the transmitter in one and the receiver in the other (Baker et al., 2007). Different subsurface sections are imaged between the two boreholes by moving the antennas relative to each other at different increments (Fig. 2.4c). According to Baker et al. (2007), this method operates in transmission mode rather than the

reflection mode since the energy detected at the receiver has transmitted through the subsurface rather than reflecting from it.

2.4.6 GPR data processing and Interpretation

A radargram is a visual representation of the reflected signals captured during GPR field survey. It shows how the radar waves interact with subsurface materials and the variations in reflected signals as they encounter different materials (Daniels, 2000). In a radargram, buried objects often appear as hyperbolas, while subsurface layers are seen as horizontally continuous reflector signals (Davis et al., 1989).

Subsurface structure is clearly imaged by processing of GPR data which removes noise and amplifies signals. Any deviation from the intended data, including disruptions from known or unknown sources (e.g. cell phones, power lines, plant roots, etc.), is referred to as noise. Coherent and non-coherent noise are the two primary categories. In GPR, data processing involves applying various filters and processes -dewow filter, background removal filter, time-gain function, just to mention a few - to enhance resolution and visibility of subsurface materials (Daniels, 2000; Baker et al., 2007).

2.4.7 Advantages and Limitations of GPR

The Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) has proven to be effective in imaging subsurface structure with various advantages over other conventional methods, which include fast data acquisition and processing, high accuracy and resolution for shallow subsurface structure imaging and high contrast in dielectric permittivity between host material and target of interest. Despite these, the GPR has its limitations including limited depth penetration, low data quality in highly conductive and/or high moisture environments or materials, and sensitive to noise.

2.5 ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY METHOD

The Electrical Resistivity method is a geophysical technique used to investigate the Earth's subsurface (Dobrin and Savit, 1988). It measures the resistivity that results from introducing electrical currents into the earth. The composition and structure beneath the earth surface can be inferred from the data obtained from these resistivity measurements. Ohm's law, which defines how electrical potential behaves when current is applied into a conductive medium, is the essential idea underlying measurements of electrical resistivity (Busby, 2003). The potential difference helps in providing information about the subsurface heterogeneities as well as its electrical properties or characteristics (Busby, 2003). According to Ohm's law, the current (I) flow through a conductor is directly proportional to the voltage (v) applied across it:

$$\delta v \propto I, \dots\dots\dots 2.3$$

This can be, expressed as:

$$\delta v = R\delta I, \dots\dots\dots 2.4$$

The resistance of the conductor that prevents current from passing through the material is known as R, or the constant of proportionality. The resistance R is directly proportional to the conducting material's length L, and inversely proportional to its cross-sectional area, A:

$$R \propto \frac{\delta L}{\delta A}, \dots\dots\dots 2.5$$

$$R = \rho \frac{\delta L}{\delta A}, \dots\dots\dots 2.6$$

ρ is known as resistivity of the material. As illustrated in Figure 2.5, where A and B represent the current electrodes and M and N the potential electrodes, the field based electrical resistivity survey is frequently conducted using four or more electrodes. The potential V_M at electrode position M is the total of the potential contributions V_A and V_B from the current source A and the sink B, considering that the sink is a finite distance from the source (Fig. 2.5).

Figure 2.5: Electrical configuration employed in ERT with A and B being the current electrodes and M and N being potential electrodes (Schlumberger, 1920)

Thus:

$$V_M = V_A + V_B, \dots\dots\dots 2.7$$

$$V_M = \frac{\rho l}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right), \dots\dots\dots 2.8$$

Similarly, at N

$$V_N = \frac{\rho l}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right), \dots\dots\dots 2.9$$

Where r_A and $R_B = s - \frac{a}{2}$, thus the distance between A and M and B and N respectively and r_B and $R_A = s + \frac{a}{2}$, representing the distance between A and N and B and M respectively (Fig. 2.5).

The potential difference (∇V) between the electrodes positioned at M and N is obtained by:

$$\nabla V = V_M - V_N = \frac{\rho l}{2\pi} \left(\left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right) \right), \dots\dots\dots 2.10$$

Making ρ the subject, equation 2.10 can be written as:

$$\rho = \frac{2\pi \nabla v}{\left[\left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right) \right] I}, \dots\dots\dots 2.11$$

If $k = \frac{2\pi}{\left[\left(\frac{1}{r_A} - \frac{1}{r_B} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{R_A} - \frac{1}{R_B} \right) \right]}, \dots\dots\dots 2.12$

Where k is the geometrical coefficient, then the apparent resistivity, ρ_a can be written as:

$$\rho_a = \frac{k \nabla v}{I}, \dots\dots\dots 2.13$$

Variations in subsurface resistivity are primarily determined by lithology and their conditions. The conditions are affected by factors such as water content, porosity, salinity in porous media, temperature, and mineral composition. Typically, igneous and metamorphic rocks have high resistivity values that decreases as porosity increases. Nonetheless, resistivity does not always align with porosity due to variations in mineral composition and pore geometry. Higher temperatures generally reduce resistivity by enhancing ion and electron mobility, particularly in fluid-containing rocks, while lower temperatures increase resistivity; similarly, rocks with metallic minerals (e.g., pyrite, magnetite) exhibit lower resistivity due to their conductive properties, whereas non-metallic minerals (e.g. quartz, calcite) contribute to higher resistivity (Palacky, 1987). Table 2.4 shows the range of resistivities of different earth materials.

Table 2.4: Geological materials and their resistivities (Telford, 1990)

Rock Type	Resistivity (Ωm)	Rock Type	Resistivity (Ωm)
Granite	$3 \times 10^2 - 10^6$	Gravel (dry)	1.4×10^4
Granite (weathered)	$0.03 - 5.0 \times 10^3$	Gravel (saturated)	1×10^2
Quartz	$3 \times 10^2 - 10^6$	Mudstone	20 – 120
Consolidated shale	$0.02 - 2.0 \times 10^3$	Siltstone	20 – 150
Sandstone	$0.2 - 500 \times 10^3$	Slate	$0.006 - 400 \times 10^6$
Clays	$1.0 - 10^2$		

2.5.1 Depth of Investigation (DoI)

A crucial component required for a reliable interpretation of the recorded apparent resistivity in geo-electrical resistivity surveys is the depth of investigation (DoI). Vozoff (1981) indicated that a relationship exists between the depth of investigation and the current electrode spacing (AB). Although it is generally accepted that increasing the electrode spread leads to a greater depth of investigation, the correlation between the depth of investigation and the current electrode spread (AB) is inconclusive (Parasnis, 1997). Field observations show that, the Schlumberger depth factor (AB/2) is not accurate enough, and several researchers have come up with different relationships, including 0.125AB (Roy and Apparao, 1971), 0.190AB (Edwards, 1977), 0.192AB (Barker, 1989) from field and laboratory studies. To determine the appropriate depth of investigation for electrical resistivity measurements, Asare et al. (2024) carried out a study. The results obtained showed that the depth of investigation for Wenner and Schlumberger were 0.258 and 0.267 of the electrodes spread (AB), respectively and 0.22 for dipole-dipole according to the Terrameter LS protocol. Since the depth is roughly twenty-five (25) percent of AB, a depth factor of 0.26 could be applied when estimating the depth of investigation from geo-electric resistivity surveys.

2.5.2 Electrode Arrays

There are different configurations for the electrical resistivity method that may be employed based on specific needs and objectives. These configurations commonly employ four colinear electrodes, and include:

- Wenner Array: In this array, the electrodes are equally spaced (Fig. 2.6), and it is commonly used for shallow investigations (Reynolds, 2011). The apparent resistivity (ρ_a) using the Wenner array is determined by equation 2.14:

$$\rho_a = 2\pi a \frac{V}{I} \dots\dots\dots 2.14$$

Figure 2.6: An image of Wenner Array for ERT

- Schlumberger Array: In this array (Fig. 2.7), the distance between the current electrodes (A & B) is greater than that of the potential electrodes (M & N) but the distance between A & M is the same as B & N. This configuration allows for flexibility during data

collection since the current electrodes can be moved farther apart to increase the depth of investigation while keeping the potential electrodes fixed (Loke, 1997). Equation 2.15 is utilised to determine the apparent resistivity (ρ_a) in the Schlumberger array:

$$\rho_a = \frac{\pi(s^2 - a^2)/4}{a} \cdot \frac{\Delta V}{I} \dots\dots\dots 2.15$$

Figure 2.7: Schlumberger configuration for ERT.

- Dipole-Dipole Array: Two pairs of electrodes with equal distances are used and the distance between the two dipoles varies (Fig. 2.8). It is often used in detailed subsurface imaging or where high-resolution data is needed (Loke, 2001) and its apparent resistivity determined by equation 2.16:

$$\rho = 2\pi (a)(2 + n)(1 + n)(n) \left(\frac{\Delta V}{I}\right) \dots\dots\dots 2.16$$

Figure 2.8: Dipole-Dipole configuration for ERT.

2.5.3 Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT)

ERT provides a comprehensive assessment of subsurface structure that considers both horizontal and vertical extent. It involves deploying numerous electrodes over a wide area to gather apparent resistivity data and generate images of subsurface features. The ERT relies on the earth's response to electrical current flow providing insights into soil properties, composition, and moisture content. In the ERT, the dipole-dipole configuration is frequently preferred for its effectiveness in mapping vertical structures, deeper depth of investigation, multichannel capability, and convenience in data acquisition as compared to other arrays, making it a popular choice for many applications (Loke, 2001); hence, the dipole-dipole configuration will be utilised in acquiring data in this project. ERT data is collected by placing

multiple electrodes on the ground surface of a site in a specific array. An electric current is injected into the ground through one pair of electrodes, while potential differences are measured using other electrode pairs. Measurements are taken at various locations along a survey line or grid to cover the area of interest. Once the data is collected, it undergoes preprocessing steps to remove noise and correct for instrument drift. This involves applying various filters and calibration procedures to ensure the quality of the data. The next step involves using mathematical models to simulate the flow of electrical currents through the subsurface based on the measured data and the known electrode configurations. Forward modelling predicts the expected resistivity distribution for a given subsurface structure. In 2D forward modelling, RES2DMOD software is used (Loke, 2003). Inverse modelling, or inversion, is the process of repeatedly adjusting the resistivity distribution within the subsurface model until it matches the observed data as closely as possible. This involves solving an optimization problem to find the subsurface resistivity distribution that explains the measured data. RES2DINVx64 software is used for a 2D inversion while the RES3DINVx64 is for 3D inversion (Loke, 2003). The inverted resistivity model is analysed to derive significant insights regarding the subsurface structure and characteristics. This process could entail recognizing geological attributes, outlining subsurface structure, charting the flow of groundwater, or identifying irregularities like contaminant concentrations.

2.5.4 Advantages and Limitations of ERT

Amongst the various geophysical methods, the ERT has proven to be effective in imaging subsurface structure with various advantages, which include good depth penetration, multichannel capability, and effectiveness in mapping both vertical and horizontal structures. Despite these, the ERT has its limitation which include limited resolution in shallow subsurface environments.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this project, five distinct sites (Independence Hall, Administration, Wiwi, Prince of Wales Park, and Pool side) as shown in Figure 3.1 were chosen within the KNUST campus, with a traverse line delineated at each site and both GPR and ERT performed on each of the traverse lines. This is done to allow direct comparison between ERT and GPR results.

Figure 3.1: Images of the study sites

3.1 ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY TOMOGRAPHY (ERT)

The ABEM Terrameter with LUND Imaging system (Fig. 3.2) and its accessories (electrodes, jumper cables, GPS, hammers) were used to acquire data from the field. The Terrameter, which operates through an electric imaging system is the core component of the ERT setup. Despite other geophysical devices, the ABEM Terrameter with LUND Imaging system remains a leading device for geophysical subsurface investigation (Loke, 1999).

3.1.1 Data Acquisition

The system, including the ABEM Terrameter and the LUND Imaging device, was utilised with a multielectrode array consisting of 81 electrodes. For data acquisition, the 81 electrodes were

arranged using the dipole-dipole array along five traverse lines which were investigated: all of them 200 m long except Line 2, which was 140 m; the depth of investigation for the 200 and 140 m lines were approximately 40 and 35 m, respectively with inter-electrode spacing of 2.5 m for the 200-m lines, and 1.75 m for Line 2. After the electrodes were planted in the ground, and the jumpers, fixed to its respective take-out position to the multi-core cable, the terrameter was configured by selecting the electrode array (i.e., dipole-dipole) and inter-electrode spacing. The Terrameter then measured the apparent resistivity values from different electrode pairs.

Figure 3.2: The ABEM Terrameter and its accessory components

3.1.2 Data Processing

After data collection, pre-processing steps were conducted to remove data outliers. This involved applying various calibration procedures to ensure data quality. The RES2DINV software was used to process the raw 2D resistivity values, generating a 2D image depicting the true subsurface resistivity distribution. Bad data points (outliers) were identified and removed, and inverse resistivity model generated. The goal of inversion was to minimize the differences between the calculated and measured apparent resistivity values by adjusting resistivity model blocks using the correlation plot (Fig. A1 – A4, appendix) -which shows how best the calculated apparent resistivities fit the measured apparent resistivities- and dissimilarity measured using root mean square (RMS) error (Loke, 2016).

3.2 GROUND PENETRATING RADAR (GPR)

The MALA GPR system, which was used in the GPR data acquisition, is made up of the unshielded rough terrain antenna, monitor, and the MALA control unit (Fig. 3.3). The Rough Terrain Antenna (RTA) is a good choice for low frequency surveys along different terrains because it allows for deeper penetration. In GPR, data acquired during field survey is displayed on the MALA monitor and the ReflexW is the main software utilised for processing.

3.2.1 Data Acquisition

A 50 MHz rough terrain antenna was equipped to gather GPR data using the time triggering acquisition mode with a time interval of 0.050 s to transmit radar signals along 200 m traverse lines at line 1, 3, 4 and 5 and 140 m traverse line along line 2. The unshielded rough terrain antenna and monitor were connected to the control unit and placed in a backpack on the field personnel and towed along the traverse lines to investigate a depth of 40 m. Keying in essential parameters such as velocity (i.e., 0.1 m/ns) data gathering mode, and antenna frequency allowed for the configuration of the MALA GPR System.

Figure 3.3: Image of the MALA system and its various components (MALA Geoscience, 2003)

3.2.2 Data Processing

A display that closely resembles a subsurface image is created by processing GPR data, with anomalies corresponding to objects of interest positioned in their correct spatial locations. After data collection, appropriate processes were applied, and data displayed using ReflexW software. The processes applied included the static correction, time gain, dewow, background removal filter, and fk migration creating a 2D image of the subsurface (Baker et al., 2007). The dewow filter eliminates low frequency noise caused by GPR signal penetrating deep into the ground and enhances high-frequency signals, improving resolution and target visibility (Davis and Annan, 1989). Static correction corrects for stationary noise and disturbances in the data, ensuring stable baseline and removes effects of varying soil conditions, topography, and instrument drift (Davis and Annan, 1989). Time gain applies an amplification to the data, increasing the gain with time. This helps to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio, improve visibility of deeper structures, and reduce the effect of signal decay (Davis and Annan, 1989).. Background removal filter removes events or noise with a slope near zero highlighting anomalies and targets making it easier to identify features of interest (Davis and Annan, 1989).

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section entails ERT and GPR results at various study sites (KNUST Independence Hall, Administration, Wiwi, Prince of Wales Park, Pool side). The colour scale of the ERT represents a range of resistivities and the horizontal axis represents the distance along the traverse line with the vertical axis showing the depth for both GPR and ERT.

4.1 LINE 1 ERT AND GPR RESULTS (INDEPENDENCE HALL)

From Figure 4.1, three resistivity zones can be discerned -mixture of very low to low resistivity ($<2900 \Omega m$), high resistivity ($2900 - 34600 \Omega m$) and very high resistivity ($>34600 \Omega m$).

Figure 4.1: ERT pseudo section along Line 1 (Independence Hall)

The mixture of very low to low resistivity ($<2900 \Omega m$) zone occurs at the surface and extends to a depth of about 5 m from the surface. At approximately 25 and 40 m along the traverse line, the very low to low resistivity ($<2900 \Omega m$) extends up to a depth of 10 and 20 m from the surface respectively, suggesting the presence of a fracture. At approximately 50 – 100 m and 110 – 160 m along the traverse line lies the very high resistivity zone ($>34600 \Omega m$) extending 5 – 35 m in depth beneath the very low to low resistivity zone. High resistivity zone ($2900 - 34600 \Omega m$) at approximately 100 – 110 m along the traverse line extends from a depth of 5 – 40 m and at 82.5 – 115 m along the traverse line extends from a depth of 35 – 40 m. This zone suggests the presence of a fracture.

The radargram (Fig. 4.2) consists of three distinctive layers: Layer 1 with strong reflections, Layer 2 showing moderately strong reflections and Layer 3 of weak reflections. Layer 1 extends from the surface to an approximate depth of 5 m; layer 2 from 5 - 20 m and layer 3 is seen from a depth beyond 20 m. A continuous reflector which extends horizontally across the radar diagram can be observed at an approximate depth of 5 and 20 m, which indicates a subsurface boundary. The strong hyperbolic reflections observed at shallow depth is influenced by the presence of surface structures, in this case trees.

Figure 4.2: GPR radargram along Line 1 (Independence Hall)

Comparing ERT and GPR images, mixture of very low and low resistivity zone (ERT) which appears to correspond to layer 1 of strong reflections (GPR) extending from the surface to an approximate depth of 5 m could be inferred as a completely weathered granitic unit with variations in material properties. The very high resistivity zone corresponds to layer 2 of moderately strong reflections of approximately 5 – 20 m depth suggesting the presence of a highly weathered granitic unit with less variations in material properties as compared to the soil. High resistivity zone (ERT) which corresponds to layer 3 of weak reflections (GPR) extending from 20 m and beyond can possibly be a slightly weathered to fresh granitic unit (suspected to be bedrock).

4.2 LINE 2 ERT AND GPR RESULTS (KNUST ADMINISTRATION)

Figure 4.3 shows three zones of resistivity: very low to low resistivity ($<1120 \Omega\text{m}$), high resistivity ($1120 - 27100 \Omega\text{m}$) and very high resistivity ($>27100 \Omega\text{m}$) zones.

Figure 4.3: ERT pseudo section along Line 2 (KNUST Administration)

The very low to low resistivity zone ($<1120 \Omega\text{m}$) covers the entire surface and extends from the surface to a depth of approximately 5m below the surface. At approximately 28m (fracture zone) along the traverse line, low resistivity zone extends up to a depth of 10m causing a break

in the very high resistivity zone. Approximately 35 to 112 m along the traverse line lies the very high resistivity zone ($>27100 \Omega\text{m}$) which extends from a depth of 5 - 20 m beneath the low resistivity. At 56.8 - 84.8 m along the traverse line, high resistivity zone ($1120 - 27100 \Omega\text{m}$) extends from a depth of 20 - 30 m beneath the very high resistivity zone.

The radargram (Fig. 4.4) reveals three distinct layers with varying reflection strengths: strong reflections are visible from the surface to an approximate depth of 5 m (Layer 1); moderately strong reflections are observed from 5 m – 20 m depth (Layer 2) and low reflections are seen at 20 m depth and beyond (Layer 3). Continuous reflectors that extend horizontally across the radargram can be seen at an approximate depth of 5 m and 20 m which indicate the layer boundaries. Strong hyperbolic reflections in the radargram are because of reflections from surface materials such as trees.

Figure 4.4: GPR radargram along Line 2 (Administration)

The very low to low resistivity zone (ERT) and layer 1 of strong reflections (GPR) which extends from the surface to 5m depth suggests a completely weathered granitic unit (mixture of sand and clay); very high resistivity zone and layer 2 of moderately strong reflections (5 – 20 m) could be a highly weathered dry granitic unit; high resistivity zone and layer 3 with weak reflection signals (beyond 20 m) suggest the presence of a slightly weathered unit (suspected to be the bedrock).

4.3 LINE 3 ERT AND GPR RESULTS (WIWD)

The pseudo section (Fig. 4.5) shows three main zones of resistivity: low resistivity ($<900 \Omega\text{m}$), high resistivity ($900 - 20800 \Omega\text{m}$) and very high resistivity ($>20800 \Omega\text{m}$). Approximately 5 -

55 m distance along the traverse line extending from 0 -20 m depth shows low resistivity zones with pockets of both very high and high resistivities. From 55-200 m along the traverse line at a depth of approximately 0-20 m shows very high resistivity zone with pockets of high resistivity zones near surface. Approximately 52.5 – 140 m distance at a depth 20-40 m show a zone of high resistivity. Fracture occurs at a traverse of approximately 50m with an aquifer occurring at a depth of 10 - 20 m.

Figure 4.5: ERT pseudo section along Line 3 (Wiwi)

Figure 4.6 depicts three layers of different reflection strengths: top layer with strong reflections, middle layer with moderately strong reflections and bottom layer with weak reflections. The top layer extends to a depth of 5 m from the surface. The middle layer extends from 5 - 20 m. A continuous reflector signal which shows a subsurface boundary is observed at approximately 5 and 20 m and it spans across the radargram. The bottom layer extends from below the reflector to approximately 40 m. Strong hyperbolic reflections observed in the radargram are because of surface materials like trees.

Figure 4.6: GPR results along Line 3 (Wiwi)

Comparing ERT and GPR images, mixture of low and high resistivity zone (ERT) which corresponds to the top layer (GPR) extending from the surface to an approximate depth of 5 m suggests the completely weathered unit; very high resistivity zone (5 – 20 m) corresponds to moderately strong reflections (middle layer) inferring the presence of highly weathered granitic unit. High resistivity zone which appears to correspond to weak reflections (bottom layer) extending from 20 m and beyond can possibly be the bedrock. The weak reflection signals could indicate a moderately to slightly weathered granitic unit.

4.4 LINE 4 ERT AND GPR RESULTS (PRINCE OF WALES PARK)

The pseudo section (Fig. 4.7) depicts two resistivity zones: Very low to low resistivity (<660 Ωm) and high resistivity (>1960 Ωm).

Figure 4.7: ERT results along Line 4 (PWP)

The high resistivity zone (>1960 Ωm) extends from approximately a distance of 20 – 200 m along the traverse line with a depth of 0 – 5 m from the surface. At 130 – 150 m along the traverse line, high resistivity zone extends to 30 m depth from the surface. The very low to low resistivity zone (<660 Ωm) lies approximately 5 - 125 m along the traverse line at a depth of 5 – 40 m (suspected to be an aquifer zone) from the surface with pockets of very low resistivity and high resistivity occurring at 40, 70, 90, 102.5 and 152.5 m.

The radar diagram (Fig. 4.8) consists of three distinctive layers: Layer 1 (strong reflections), layer 2 (moderately strong reflections) and layer 3 (weak reflections). Layer 1 has strong reflections which are visible from the surface up to about 5 m depth, moderately strong reflections (Layer 2) are seen from a depth of 5 - 20 m. The weak reflections (Layer 3) extend beyond the depth of 20 m. A continuous reflector signal which extends horizontally across the radar diagram can be observed at an approximate depth of 5 and 20 m beneath the surface, which indicates a subsurface boundary. The strong hyperbolic reflections observed in the radargram are because of surface materials like trees.

Comparing the ERT and GPR images, the high resistivity zone (ERT) and the strong reflections (layer 1) at the surface of the profile at Prince of Wales Park is inferred to be a completely weathered unit. The high resistivity zone showing at the surface (0 – 5 m) is suspected to be due to the presence of sand and gravels with low moisture content, while the strong reflections at the surface are because of materials of different dielectric properties. The moderately strong reflections (layer 2) of the GPR corresponds to the mixture of high and low resistivity zone (5 – 20 m) which is suspected to be a highly weathered granitic unit whereas the weak reflections (layer 3) correspond to the low to moderate resistivity at the base which is likely to represent the bedrock with varying degree of weathering.

Figure 4.8: Radargram of Line 4 (Prince of Wales Park)

4.5 LINE 5 ERT AND GPR RESULTS (POOL SIDE)

Figure 4.9 depicts three zones of resistivity: low resistivity zone ($< 5900 \Omega\text{m}$), high resistivity zone (14900 - 95428 Ωm) and very high resistivity zone ($>95428 \Omega\text{m}$)

Figure 4.9: ERT results along Line 5 (Pool side)

Low resistivity ($< 5900 \Omega\text{m}$) covers 0 m to 200 m along the traverse line and extends from the surface to a depth of approximately 5 m. Beneath the low resistivity, approximately 0 – 160 m

along the traverse line, lies the high resistivity zone (14900 – 95428 Ωm) extending from a depth of 5 – 20 m and at 20 m and beyond lies a very high resistivity zone. At 60 m along the traverse line, low resistivity (<5900 Ωm) extends from the surface to an approximate depth of 25 m indicating a fracture zone and pockets of very low resistivity (<370 Ωm) occurring at 40, 45, 60, 70, 80, 130, 145 and 180 m along the traverse line.

The radargram (Fig.4.10) shows three distinct layers with varying reflection strengths: the first layer, Layer 1, consisting of strong reflections are prominent from the surface to an approximate depth of 6 m; a second layer, Layer 2, of medium reflections are equally observed from depth of 6 – 20 m and low reflections are seen at 20 m depth and beyond making up the third layer, Layer 3. Continuous horizontal reflector signature that extend horizontally across the radargram can be seen at approximate depths of 6 m and 20 m which indicate the layer boundaries.

Figure 4.10: Radargram of Line 5 (Pool side)

Comparing the GPR and ERT images, Layer 1 with its strong reflections is suspected to be a completely weathered unit; and the high contrast suggest significant differences in material properties and condition which corresponds to the low resistivity zone of the ERT image (0 – 5 m). The layer 2 consisting of moderately strong reflector response could be a possible transition zone in subsurface materials from the soil to the overburden unit of possibly highly weathered granitic unit which corresponds to the high resistivity zone (5 – 20 m) of the ERT. The third layer consisting of low reflections can be a more homogenous material with little variation in composition which is suspected to be the bedrock (fresh to slightly weathered), and it corresponds to the very high resistivity zone occurring at 20 – 40 m.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

In this project, both the Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) and Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) were successfully used to delineate subsurface resistivity distribution and layering respectively, and the images appeared to complement each reasonably well. The 2D pseudo section of ERT showed three resistivity zones -a mixture of very low and low resistivity zone extending from the surface to an approximate depth of 5 m, very high resistivity zone of 5 – 20 m depth and high resistivity zone extending beyond 20 m. The GPR survey also delineated three distinctive layers; Layer 1 of strong reflections in the radar diagram correspond to the low resistivity zones occurring at approximately 5 m depth from the surface of the pseudo section which can be inferred as a completely weathered unit. Layer 2 of moderately strong reflections, which appeared to match the very high resistivity zones of the ERT occurring at approximately 5 – 20 m depth and suggesting a highly weathered granitic unit, and the high resistivity zone beyond 20 m, which corresponds to Layer 3 of weak reflections, may possibly be moderately to slightly weathered unit (suspected to be the bedrock). This study shows that GPR and ERT images appear to match each other reasonably well, and thus the GPR can help with the interpretation of the resistivity images of the ERT, and therefore enhancing subsurface investigations.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

ERT and GPR results may have to be validated using ground truth data such as borehole logs. During inversion of ERT data, high RMS error values were observed, and the following can be recommended to avoid such errors in future studies: ensuring proper data acquisition with accurate electrode spacing and using advanced inversion techniques such as adjusting the damping factor to improve inversion results and reduce high RMS values.

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APPENDIX

